

MSP4BIO

POLICY BRIEF: JOINT POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Strengthening Marine Biodiversity Through Maritime Spatial
Planning: A Joint Agenda for Coherent Policy Action

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CALL FOR ACTION

Policymakers at all levels—regional, national, and EU-wide—must act decisively to strengthen the biodiversity dimension of Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP). As Europe advances towards the implementation of the Green Deal and the newly adopted Ocean Pact, we urge the following actions:

- **Strengthen Legal and Policy Frameworks for MSP to better integrate biodiversity objectives.**
- **Enhance Planning and Implementation Tools to ensure effective coordination and spatial prioritization.**
- **Embed Biodiversity in Sectoral Policies and Practices, from offshore energy to aquaculture and fisheries.**
- **Institutionalize Inclusive Stakeholder Engagement to support continuous, science-based, and equitable decision-making.**
- **Secure Adequate and Stable Financing, by embedding biodiversity targets into maritime policies and aligning Marine Protected Area (MPA) objectives with spatial planning strategies.**
- **Support Adaptive Management and Monitoring through long-term investment in capacity-building and data infrastructure.**

Now is the moment to act. Ongoing revisions of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive and the Maritime Spatial Planning Directive, along with the entry into force of the EU Nature Restoration Law, offer a unique window of opportunity to align MSP with the next implementation phase of the EU Ocean Pact.

We call on institutions to invest in cross-sector coordination, multi-level governance, and science-policy-society interfaces that support an ecosystem-based approach to MSP. Only by doing so can we ensure that ocean use is planned in a way that protects biodiversity, supports climate resilience, and sustains the health and productivity of Europe's seas.

Concrete and actionable recommendations can be found throughout this brief—across institutional, organizational, technical, and financial domains.

INTRODUCTION

Marine biodiversity is the foundation of healthy marine ecosystems and the key to sustaining the services they provide to society. However, despite progress under various EU and international frameworks, biodiversity loss in the marine environment continues due to fragmented governance, a lack of binding conservation targets, insufficient integration of biodiversity in marine policies in general and specifically in maritime spatial planning (MSP), and inadequate funding and data. A range of projects have contributed policy insights to address these issues, particularly through refining MPA objectives, boosting cross-sectoral coordination, and enhancing technical and institutional capacities.

This policy brief outlines a set of joint policy recommendations co-developed through MSP4BIO Science-Policy Dialogue Think thank¹ and other collaborative meetings with relevant projects: MSP4BIO, MPA Europe, CrossGov, MSP Green, REGINA-MSP, MSP-OR, and eMSP NBSR, to support the integration of biodiversity into MSP processes. These recommendations aim to address current gaps by strengthening governance structures, ensuring transparent biodiversity assessments, embedding biodiversity into sectoral performance, and enabling continuous stakeholder engagement and adequate funding.

CONTEXT & POLICY CHALLENGE

Biodiversity is a cornerstone of effective MSP, which seeks to balance ecological, economic, and social objectives in marine areas. The degradation of biodiversity undermines the ecosystem services upon which many maritime sectors depend. Current MSP practices often fall short of fully integrating biodiversity considerations due to siloed decision-making, limited data availability, and the absence of binding conservation targets.

The EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), the MSP Directive and the Nature Restoration Law, all stress the importance of safeguarding marine biodiversity. Nevertheless, implementation is inconsistent across Member States, and synergies between MSP and biodiversity policy are underutilized. Bridging this gap is essential to meet EU climate, biodiversity, and blue economy goals.

¹ Deliverable 6.3 Policy solutions for MSP based on the science-policy dialogues (<https://msp4bio.eu/>)

KEY RECOMMENDATIONS FOR POLICYMAKERS

1. HOW TO READ THIS POLICY BRIEF

This policy brief is designed to support policymakers, planners, and stakeholders working at the interface of marine biodiversity and maritime spatial planning (MSP).

The brief presents a set of harmonized policy recommendations, collected and synthesized from multiple European projects. Recommendations are grouped into four thematic categories that reflect key areas for action:

Institutional – improving governance structures and coordination

Organizational – engaging stakeholders and improving decision-making processes

Technical – tools, data, capacity, and planning practices

Resource-related – funding and investment in biodiversity and research

Each category includes concise recommendations supported by one or more projects, along with a short explanation of the action proposed. Project names are included in parentheses to highlight the sources contributing to each recommendation.

INSTITUTIONAL RECOMMENDATIONS

“STRENGTHEN MARINE BIODIVERSITY GOVERNANCE BY IMPROVING COORDINATION, INTEGRATION, AND INSTITUTIONAL CAPACITY.”

1. Establish a coordination framework

CREATE NATIONAL AND REGIONAL COORDINATION FRAMEWORKS

Establish or reinforce structures specifically dedicated to marine biodiversity coordination across governance levels. Regular inter-authority sessions help ensure that biodiversity is coherently addressed in planning at different spatial scales.

(MSP4BIO, MSP Green, MPA Europe)

REINFORCE MECHANISMS FOR THE INTEGRATION OF MSFD AND MSP IMPLEMENTATION AND ENSURE CONTINUOUS INTER-INSTITUTIONAL DIALOGUE TO ALIGN UPDATES OF PLANS, PROGRAM OF MEASURES, AND RIVER BASIN MANAGEMENT PLANS.

Facilitate communication and coordination between existing competent authorities to enhance policy coherence.

(MSP4BIO, CrossGov)

PROMOTE FISHERIES–BIODIVERSITY INTEGRATION THROUGH LOCAL PLATFORMS

Leverage existing platforms like Fisheries Local Action Groups to incorporate biodiversity objectives into fisheries policies and local development.

(CrossGov)

SUPPORT JOINT DEVELOPMENT OF EU-LEVEL RECOMMENDATIONS

Encourage earlier involvement of the European Commission in the development of joint recommendations under the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP), to ensure that biodiversity priorities are fully integrated and not weakened during the negotiation process.

(CrossGov)

FACILITATE INTERREGIONAL COMMUNITIES OF PRACTICE

Create technical networks between authorities and experts across regions to exchange experiences, tools, and good practices in integrating biodiversity into MSP.

(REGINA-MSP)

INSTITUTIONAL RECOMMENDATIONS

“STRENGTHEN MARINE BIODIVERSITY GOVERNANCE BY IMPROVING COORDINATION, INTEGRATION, AND INSTITUTIONAL CAPACITY.”

2. Mandatory biodiversity targets, assessment and reporting

STANDARDIZE CROSS-SECTORAL BIODIVERSITY ASSESSMENTS

Use existing inter-ministerial bodies to design shared reporting formats and biodiversity metrics, promoting transparency and accountability.

(MSP4BIO)

MANDATE 30% PROTECTION (INCLUDING 10% STRICT PROTECTION) IN NATIONAL MSP (OR IN REVISED MSFD)

Brings legally binding biodiversity targets into MSPD, reinforcing institutional commitment. Define strict protection at EU level, coordinate conservation measures among member states.

(MSP4BIO, CrossGov)

IMPROVE THE INTEGRATION AND USE OF MSFD CRITERIA AND VALUES IN MSP

Improve and complete threshold methods and values for GES assessment according to MSFD, and use these criteria and values as key elements and targets for Ecosystem-Based MSP.

(CrossGov)

INTRODUCE LEGALLY BINDING BIODIVERSITY REPORTING REQUIREMENTS

Make biodiversity considerations a mandatory part of policy decisions across all relevant sectors, not just environment ministries.

(MSP4BIO)

REVIEW AND UPDATE ASSESSMENT PRACTICES REGULARLY

Implement an institutional process to ensure biodiversity data, methods, and indicators remain current and relevant.

(MSP4BIO)

INSTITUTIONAL RECOMMENDATIONS

"STRENGTHEN MARINE BIODIVERSITY GOVERNANCE BY IMPROVING COORDINATION, INTEGRATION, AND INSTITUTIONAL CAPACITY."

2. Mandatory biodiversity targets, assessment and reporting

INCLUDE BIODIVERSITY TARGETS IN SECTORAL PERFORMANCE EVALUATIONS

Link sectoral goals (e.g. fisheries, transport) with measurable biodiversity outcomes to ensure alignment and accountability.

(MSP4BIO)

ALIGN FISHERIES MEASURES WITH BIODIVERSITY GOALS

Strengthen conservation outcomes by better connecting fishing-related measures (e.g. gear limits, seasonal closures, spatially based management measures) with biodiversity goals and providing for their monitoring.

(CrossGov)

ENFORCE EU DIRECTIVES AND REDUCE EXEMPTIONS

Encourage the Commission to address overuse of exemptions in MSFD and WFD through a revision, particularly where they compromise biodiversity outcomes.

(CrossGov)

INSTITUTIONAL RECOMMENDATIONS

“STRENGTHEN MARINE BIODIVERSITY
GOVERNANCE BY IMPROVING
COORDINATION, INTEGRATION, AND
INSTITUTIONAL CAPACITY.”

3. Revise MPA objectives

REDEFINE MPA OBJECTIVES USING THE SMART FRAMEWORK

Ensure MPA goals are Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound, tailored to the ecological characteristics and conservation needs of each area.

(MSP4BIO)

ALIGN MPA MANAGEMENT WITH MSP PROCESSES

Establish formal coordination and cooperation mechanisms between MPA managers and MSP authorities, enabling spatial planning to support biodiversity inside and outside MPAs.

(MSP4BIO)

CONDUCT REGULAR MPA EFFECTIVENESS EVALUATIONS

Monitor and assess MPA performance systematically, and adjust objectives and management actions based on outcomes and changing ecological conditions.

(MSP4BIO)

SUPPORT MPA DESIGNATION AND MANAGEMENT THROUGH SPATIAL PLANNING TOOLS

Use MSP to help identify, designate, and manage MPAs and OECMs by integrating ecological data and planning measures.

(MSP Green)

RECOGNIZE THE ECOLOGICAL ROLE OF INDIVIDUAL MPAS IN REGIONAL NETWORKS

Consider how MPAs function as source or sink areas within wider ecological networks, and plan and manage them accordingly to maximize species abundance and connectivity.

(MPA Europe)

ORGANIZATIONAL RECOMMENDATIONS

“STAKEHOLDERS SHOULD BE EMBEDDED IN THE MSP PROCESS FROM START TO FINISH TO ENSURE LEGITIMACY, LOCAL RELEVANCE, AND ADAPTIVE GOVERNANCE.”

1 Continuous stakeholder engagement

Establish permanent stakeholder engagement platforms

Formalize ongoing structures for input from local communities, civil society, and researchers, allowing early and continued participation in MSP processes. (MSP4BIO, MSP Green)

Integrate stakeholder visions and scenario building

Foster long-term collaboration by involving stakeholders in the creation of shared visions and spatial futures, rather than just reacting to fixed plans. (MSP Green)

Ensure participation of underrepresented groups

Proactively engage stakeholders often left out of formal planning, especially small-scale fisheries and community-based organizations. (CrossGov, MSP Green, REGINA-MSP)

Apply structured feedback loops

Design stakeholder processes that not only collect input, but also provide feedback on how stakeholder views shaped final outcomes. (MSP-OR)

2 Legally binding biodiversity targets

Introduce legally binding biodiversity objectives in sectoral policies

Require sectors such as energy, fisheries, and transport to incorporate measurable biodiversity targets directly into their operational and strategic planning. (MSP4BIO)

Link biodiversity targets with human activities

Establish clear mechanisms that connect planning decisions and sectoral developments to biodiversity outcomes through enforceable legal instruments. (MSP4BIO)

Strengthen enforcement and monitoring mechanisms

Ensure that legally binding targets are backed by monitoring frameworks and compliance tools to track progress and take corrective action when needed. (MSP4BIO)

TECHNICAL RECOMMENDATIONS

“EFFECTIVE BIODIVERSITY INTEGRATION IN MSP DEPENDS ON CAPACITY BUILDING, DATA, GUIDANCE, AND ADAPTATION TO CLIMATE CHANGE.”

Deliver ecosystem-based training programs

Train planners and decision-makers in ecosystem-based management (EBM), spatial data interpretation, adaptive planning, and biodiversity law to improve implementation.
(MSP4BIO, MSP Green)

Facilitate knowledge sharing across governance levels

Organize structured exchanges and dialogue forums across local, national, and EU levels to spread best practices and ensure coherence.
(MSP4BIO)

Develop e-learning and continuous learning modules

Offer flexible, long-term capacity-building tools to ensure that biodiversity knowledge is retained and updated across administrations.
(MSP4BIO)

Incorporate social science into planning

Use the expertise of social scientists to define relevant social data and conduct effective social impact assessments in MSP.
(MSP-OR)

Train marine sector officials beyond MSP

Provide biodiversity-relevant training also for those working in transport, energy, and fisheries to ensure coherent implementation.
(REGINA-MSP)

Capacity building for MSP practitioners

Develop clear guidelines for MPA management

Provide planners and MPA managers with practical tools covering enforcement, adaptive management, and ecological effectiveness.
(MSP4BIO)

Improve monitoring with modern tools

Invest in advanced surveillance, data collection, and feedback mechanisms to evaluate MPA performance and guide adaptive actions.
(MSP4BIO)

Integrate OECMs and spatial measures near MPAs

Define both spatial and regulatory measures, including Other Effective Area-Based Conservation Measures (OECMs), to support MPAs through MSP.
(MSP Green)

Use ecosystem service assessments in MPA planning

Apply ES assessments to explore trade-offs and support transparent, science-based negotiations with stakeholders.
(MSP-OR)

Guidelines for MPA management

TECHNICAL RECOMMENDATIONS

“EFFECTIVE BIODIVERSITY
INTEGRATION IN MSP DEPENDS ON
CAPACITY BUILDING, DATA,
GUIDANCE, AND ADAPTATION TO
CLIMATE CHANGE.”

Climate-smart MSP

Integrate climate adaptation into MSP

Embed nature-based solutions and vulnerability assessments to protect marine ecosystems from climate risks.

(MSP4BIO, MSP Green)

Use spatial planning to mitigate climate change

Identify and preserve carbon-rich areas (e.g. seabed sediments), and regulate sectoral impacts on key ecosystems through MSP.

(MPA Europe)

Model and protect climate refugia

Identify areas likely to remain suitable for biodiversity under future climate scenarios, and prioritize them in MSP and MPA design.

(MPA Europe)

Establish 'go/no-go' zones for offshore wind

Apply biophysical impact assessments to steer energy development away from ecologically sensitive areas, taking into account their potential transboundary effects and the interconnection.

(CrossGov)

Guide emerging sectors with ecosystem-based principles

Ensure the sustainable integration of new uses (e.g., blue biotech, aquaculture) into MSP through ecosystem-based planning.

(MSP-OR)

RESOURCE-RELATED RECOMMENDATIONS

“SUSTAINABLE BIODIVERSITY INTEGRATION IN MSP REQUIRES DEDICATED FUNDING AND LONG-TERM INVESTMENT IN RESEARCH AND INNOVATION.”

1. DEDICATED BIODIVERSITY FUNDING:

Allocate maritime-related tax revenues to biodiversity initiatives

Earmark a portion of taxes from marine sectors (e.g. shipping, offshore energy) to fund the implementation of National Biodiversity Strategies and MPA management.

(MSP4BIO)

Develop innovative financing mechanisms

Create funding structures that blend public and private resources, such as biodiversity offsets, conservation bonds, or blue carbon credits.

(MSP4BIO)

Establish national biodiversity funds for adaptive management

Set up dedicated national or regional funds to support flexible, evidence-based responses to changing biodiversity conditions.

(MSP4BIO)

Link access to funds with environmental conditions

Attach biodiversity-related criteria to financial support for marine activities to ensure alignment with conservation objectives.

(CrossGov)

Shift funding from practices to performance

Redirect support from generic “sustainable management” actions toward measurable biodiversity outcomes, such as nutrient load reductions or species recovery.

(CrossGov)

Ensure funding for biodiversity area designations and working groups

Provide resources for both the identification of new MPAs/OECMs and the collaborative groups that plan and manage them.

(MSP Green)

RESOURCE-RELATED RECOMMENDATIONS

“SUSTAINABLE BIODIVERSITY INTEGRATION IN MSP REQUIRES DEDICATED FUNDING AND LONG-TERM INVESTMENT IN RESEARCH AND INNOVATION.”

2. INVESTMENT IN RESEARCH:

Support long-term biodiversity monitoring

Fund multi-year research programs that track ecosystem health and species trends, forming a basis for adaptive MSP and MPA management.

(MSP4BIO)

Encourage interdisciplinary methods and tools

Invest in research that integrates natural and social sciences to better understand ecological change and stakeholder behavior.

(MSP4BIO)

Promote cross-border scientific collaboration

Facilitate international partnerships to fill knowledge gaps in transboundary marine regions and jointly develop decision-support tools.

(MSP4BIO)

Improve cumulative impact modelling and climate tracking

Expand data collection and simulation tools to understand combined pressures on ecosystems under climate change.

(MSP Green)

Strengthen biodiversity knowledge in under-sampled marine areas

Support empirical field research in less-studied parts of Europe's seas to improve the spatial accuracy of species models and conservation priorities.

(MPA Europe)

RESOURCE-RELATED RECOMMENDATIONS

“SUSTAINABLE BIODIVERSITY INTEGRATION IN MSP REQUIRES DEDICATED FUNDING AND LONG-TERM INVESTMENT IN RESEARCH AND INNOVATION.”

3. DATA ACCESSIBILITY AND DECISION SUPPORT TOOLS:

Enhance cross-sectoral collaboration

Enhance cross-sectoral collaboration by developing shared databases and tools that bridge data gaps and support joint planning among biodiversity, fisheries, energy, and other maritime sector authorities.
(MSP4BIO, CrossGov)

Invest in user-friendly and interoperable data platforms

Build decision-support tools that allow cross-sector and cross-border use of biodiversity and planning data.
(MSP4BIO, MSP Green)

Standardize biodiversity data collection

Harmonize data methodologies across EU Member States to improve comparability and policy integration.
(MSP4BIO)

Ensure biodiversity datasets feed into global repositories

Encourage countries to share species and habitat data with global platforms like OBIS and GBIF to improve modelling and access.
(MPA Europe)

Strengthen the role of data in marine decision-making

Emphasize the use of reliable biodiversity data when allocating fishing rights or setting spatial regulations.
(CrossGov)

Strengthen the role of cross-sectoral, multi-actor Science to Policy to Society Interfaces (SPSI) in decision making

Establish SPSIs platforms and boundary organizations or reinforce existing ones to strengthen the mutual dialogue between the scientific communities, policymakers in various policy domains, and the civil society for exchanges, co-evolution, and joint construction of knowledge supporting marine decision-making.
(CrossGov)

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